

**ANALYTICAL STUDY OF VARIOUS STORAGE FACILITIES WITH
REFERENCE TO AGRICULTURE PRODUCE OF THE FARMERS,
RETAILERS AND COMMISSION AGENTS**

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Introduction:

Storage is a source of which increase benefit to the all types of respondents whether it is farmer, retailer or commission agent which further gives the more benefit of the high returns for the Agri produce. Hence the researcher is interested to find out the various storage facilities with reference to agriculture produce in Nanded district.

Research Methodology of the study:

In order to collect the primary data following methodology has been adopted. The investigation in economics starts with selection of appropriate numbers of respondent's preparation of scheduled selection of proper tools of analysis for the collection of data. Details regarding the plan of investigation i.e. sampling design, nature & sources of data, Statistical tools & Techniques etc. adopted for the study are presented in this paper under the following heads:

Sampling design:

Since the study has aimed at finding out the storage facilities with reference to agriculture produce in Nanded district, the sample for the study necessarily involves the selection of cultivators as well as marketing intermediaries for gathering relevant data on the above aspects of the study.

In this study for the selection of cultivators multistage sampling techniques have been followed with district as the first unit, tehsils as the second unit and villages as the third and final unit.

Selection of district:

The agro climatic conditions prevailing in Nanded district of the Marathwada region in Maharashtra state are congenial for agriculture. Similarly, there is a good network of canals in the district, which enables to increase water table of the wells in the command area of the canals. This offers good scope for agriculture development. Hence, Nanded district has been selected purposively for the present study.

Selection of tehsils:

There are sixteen tehsils in Nanded District and all the talukas are selected as samples for the present study.

Selection of villages:

In this study, five villages from each taluka are selected randomly. These total samples villages are 80 from sixteen talukas have been selected for the present study.

Selection of farmers:

20 farmers from each taluka totaling 320 have been selected randomly (purposive random selection method). The list of farmers of selected villages has been obtained from the land holding.

Selection of markets:

Agricultural Production in Nanded district is marketed either in Nanded or Hyderabad market. Hence, the researcher has been selected as market of the production area and the latter as market of the consuming area.

Selection of market functionaries:

From Nanded market 10 commission agents and 30 retailers and 2 commission agents and 10 retailers from each taluka level market have been selected randomly. The Primary cross sections data have been collected by the survey method through conducting personal interviews of head of the respondent family. The data have been gathered with the help of well-structured specially designed pre-tested schedules separately for agriculture crop cultivators and each marketing functionary involved in the problems & prospectus of agriculture.

Objective of the study:

To identify the various storage facilities with reference to agriculture produce of the farmers, retailers and commission agents in Nanded district.

Hypothesis of the study:

In-depth qualitative rather than quantitative information was used for the purpose to answer the research questions. Farmers, Retailers and the commission agents were interviewed to gather information.

Following is the hypothesis of the present study.

Farmers, retailers and commission agents of Nanded district are facing the problem of storage facilities with reference to agriculture produce.

Statistical Tools & Techniques:

The following tools are used for analysis and interpretation of the study as wherever they are suitable / applicable.

- A. Percentages
- B. Ratios
- C. Growth Rates
- D. Chi-Square Analysis
- E. Figures

Storage Facilities with the respondents:

Storage is a source of which increase benefit to the all types of respondents whether it is farmer, retailer or commission agent which further gives the more benefit of the high returns for the Agri produce.

TABLE
STORAGE FACILITIES WITH THE RESPONDENTS

Sr. No.	Storage Facilities	No. of Respondents			Total	%
		Farmers	Retailers	Commission Agents		
01	House	247	64	09	320	59.26
02	Cold Storage	12	53	08	73	13.51
03	Godowns	23	51	12	86	15.93
04	Neighbor	38	12	11	61	11.30
Total		320	180	40	540	100.00

Source: - Field Survey

($X^2=151.67$, table value @ 5% level = 12.6)

Since the immemorial time house has been the main source of storage of food grains to farmers. As presented in table, 320 respondents surveyed use own house as their storage out of which 247 are farmers, 64 retailers and 9 commission agents which aggregated 59.26%. Cold storage house has attracted a little to the farmers, retailers and commission agents where 73 respondents stores their agri produce out of which 12 farmers, 53 retailers and 8 commission agents which aggregated 13.51% of total produce. In godown 15.93% of agri produce stores wherein 23 farmers, 51 retailers and 12 commission agents are stores their agri produce. Some of farmers, retailers and commission agents use their neighboring houses; godowns etc. to store their agri produce which is small in number grossly aggregating 11.30% wherein 38 farmers, 12 retailers and 11 commission agents.

Testing of Hypothesis:

From the calculations based on the above table, calculated value of Chi-Square is worked out as 16.71 whereas Table Value at 5% degree of freedom is 12.6. Calculated value of Chi-Square is more than the table value. Therefore the hypothesis is rejected.

Conclusion:

It can be said that the farmers, retailers and commission agents of Nanded district are not facing the problem of storage facilities with reference to agriculture produce.

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